

Sustainable Trade Toolbox

MATS Deliverable 2.3

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www.sustainable-agri-trade.eu

Summary

MATS WP2 aims to build an Analytical Framework focused on obtaining a systemic understanding of agricultural trade from a sustainability and human rights perspective. Task 2.3 feeds into the MATS Analytical Framework by identifying relevant frameworks, approaches, methods, and tools to systematically analyze the agricultural trade systems from a sustainability perspective. This deliverable compiles a broad range of key instruments.

Relevant instruments were identified through a review process of different sources, guided by selection criteria agreed upon by MATS partners involved in WP2. Critical information was gathered, including a brief description of each instrument, its scope in terms of the food systems dimensions, key bibliographic references to delve into the instrument, and key applications in agriculture, food systems, and/or trade.

The first version of the Toolbox was developed, released, and shared with MATS partners in May 2022. This preliminary version informed the implementation of case studies, the analysis of linkages between agricultural trade, sustainability, and human well-being, and the derivation of transition pathways.

Once the MATS activities were largely advanced or fully developed, the Toolbox was revisited and updated, taking into account the lessons learned throughout the MATS project based on the 15 case studies and the analyses performed in the different Work Packages.

This deliverable will be transferred to the MATS website as a search platform to access the Tool factsheets generated in this Deliverable through a set of search criteria to make the Toolbox more user-friendly.

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¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1. Introduction

MATS WP2 aims to develop an Analytical Framework that provides theoretical and methodological guidance for MATS analyses addressing:

- The linkages between agricultural trade, sustainability, and human well-being (WP3).
- The impacts of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks on the sustainability of agricultural trade (WP4).
- The design of transition pathways for desirable change in trade relations, policies, instruments, and practices (WP5).

Task 2.3 contributes to the MATS Analytical Framework by compiling key information from relevant frameworks, approaches, methods, and tools to systematically analyze the agricultural trade systems from a sustainability perspective.

This task draws on two main sources:

- The findings from WP1, which reviewed the connections between agricultural trade, sustainability, and human well-being.
- The results from task 2.2, which analyzed the computational models used to assess agricultural trade.

The work from task 2.3 is documented in this Deliverable, a crucial step in WP2 towards building the MATS Enhanced Analytical Framework (D2.4). As the MATS project progressed, the Toolbox was revisited and updated based on the lessons learned from 15 case studies and various analyses performed across the Work Packages.

To disseminate and communicate MATS' findings, we are working to make the Toolbox accessible to a wide audience via the MATS website. This includes creating a search platform for the Tool factsheets generated in this Deliverable, using specific search criteria to enhance user-friendliness.

This Deliverable (D2.3) is framed under a food systems perspective, aligning with MATS' goal to apply rigorous systems thinking to the challenges posed by agricultural trade to sustainability and human well-being.

The report is structured as follows.

The first section introduces the food systems approach as a suitable framework for assessing agricultural trade from a systemic viewpoint. The second section describes the methodology used to identify and select the instruments for the Toolbox, detailing the process of updating the Toolbox during the final year of the MATS project, including validation with MATS key partners and consultations on the usefulness of the instruments with MATS case studies. Finally, the third section presents the Toolbox itself in its latest version.

2. Food system approach to assessing agricultural trade under a systemic view

Addressing sustainability challenges linked to food systems requires acknowledging and exploring the interdependencies that shape systems dynamics and the delivery of outcomes such as food security, environmental and economic sustainability, and human well-being across dimensions and scales (Global Panel on Agriculture and Food Systems for Nutrition, 2020).

MATS applies the rigor of systems thinking by adopting a food systems approach. This approach sheds light on the socio-economic and environmental externalities and interlinkages between agricultural trade and how food is produced, processed, and consumed (FAO, WFP, & IFAD, 2012; Global Panel on Agriculture and Food Systems for Nutrition, 2016, 2020; HLPE, 2017, 2020; IPES-Food, 2015, 2017, 2018, 2021). This enables the identification of key leverage points to foster positive and reduce negative impacts of agricultural trade on sustainability and human well-being, thus informing more coherent agricultural trade policies and actions.

The food systems approach is operationalized through frameworks designed to guide food systems agents – farmers, practitioners, investors, decision-makers, researchers, enterprises, etc. – in addressing food and agriculture challenges more systemically, including those posed by agricultural trade.

Food systems frameworks have incorporated ideas and practices from systems thinking and complexity science (STCS) to deal with complex situations. The three primary contributions from food systems frameworks can be summarized as:

- 1) Making sense of broader sustainability and human well-being issues related to agricultural trade.
- 2) Exploring food systems' dynamic behavior.
- 3) Acknowledging the agency's role in framing and addressing problematic situations in food systems.

These three main contributions are elaborated upo below.

The food systems approach is introduced to support and inform a more systemic use of the various tools, methods, frameworks, and indicators comprised in the Toolbox. Different tools and methods can address diverse agricultural trade issues or opportunities framed differently by agents with diverse interests, values, expectations, and power. Each tool focuses on specific dimensions and elements of the system (economy, human rights, environmental sustainability, livelihoods, etc.).

This Deliverable aims to cover a broad range of tools that analyze and advance agricultural trade as a lever for sustainability. At the same time, it seeks to:

- Support the use of these tools in more systemic ways.
- Acknowledge the intricated and complex multidimensional nature of agricultural trade issues.
- Recognize the emergent and non-linear dynamics of these issues.
- Acknowledge the role of agents in framing situations, challenges, opportunities, and pathways forward.

3.1. Make sense of broader sustainability and human well-being issues related to agricultural trade.

To promote a comprehensive understanding of food systems, food systems frameworks list and describe elements that help make sense of complex food-related challenges and their interrelations, impacting human well-being and sustainability. Food systems are broadly understood as a set of activities – from production to consumption of food – embedded and interrelated with the broader human, social, economic, and natural context. This multidimensional context and diverse set of drivers influence how food is produced, processed, marketed, and consumed, and their impacts on food security, social welfare, and environmental sustainability (Béné et al., 2019; Connolly-Boutin & Smit, 2016; Dury, Bendjebbar, Hainzelin, Giordano, & Bricas, 2019; Ericksen, 2008; HLPE, 2017; van Berkum, Dengerink, & Ruben, 2018).

The food system approach broadens the scope of analysis of food and agriculture-related issues. It demonstrates how activities and outputs from the value chain feedback into the environmental and socio-economic drivers that, in turn, affect those activities and outputs (Bortoletti & Lomax, 2019; Ericksen, 2008; Hubeau et al., 2017; TEEB, 2018; van Berkum, Dengerink, & Ruben, 2018). Additionally, it explores the emergent and often unpredictable behavior of food systems by revealing synergies and trade-offs between their elements - either drivers, value chain activities, or outcomes (Béné et al., 2019; IOM & NRC, 2015; iPES Food, 2015; Nguyen, 2018; UNEP, 2016).

3.2. Account for food system dynamics

Food systems exhibit dynamic, non-linear, and often unpredictable behavior that can be understood only by exploring their trajectory through time. Some food systems frameworks use the concepts of vulnerability and resilience to

describe the role of key variables – known as control variables – in driving food systems toward stability or transformation (Allen & Prosperi, 2016; Connolly-Boutin & Smit, 2016; Jackson, McNamara, & Witt, 2020; TEEB, 2018; Vallejo-Rojas et al., 2016; van Berkum et al., 2018). Transformations involve changes in the resilience of food systems (IOM & NRC, 2015), which occur when a tipping point in control variables is reached (van Berkum et al., 2018).

3.3. Acknowledge the role of agency in how problematic situations in food systems are framed and addressed.

The same situation can be understood differently, depending on who is seeing it and their primary values, goals, interests, and concerns (Béné et al., 2019; Bortoletti & Lomax, 2019; iPES Food, 2015; UNEP, 2016). Food systems frameworks promote spaces for dialogue and exchange among agents with different perspectives to get a comprehensive understanding of the situation to be addressed (Halbe & Adamowski, 2019; Hubeau et al., 2017; Posthumus et al., 2018; TEEB, 2018).

In creating spaces for discussion and joint reflection, the influence of governance mechanisms and power relations on decision-making about how problems are framed and addressed should be acknowledged (HLPE, 2017; Nguyen, 2018; UNEP, 2016). Additionally, it should be acknowledged that any decision implies setting boundaries, which requires determining which values, interests, and expectations to prioritize when describing the situation and identifying ways to achieve the desired transformation (Allen & Prosperi, 2016; Ericksen, 2008b; IOM & NRC, 2015; TEEB, 2018).

3. Methodology

This section outlines the five-stage methodology adopted to design a Sustainable Trade Toolbox that informs MATS analyses from a systems perspective. The main goal is to better understand and address the challenges posed by the agricultural trade to sustainability, human well-being, and human rights. The Toolbox encompasses various instruments ranging from guiding principles and methodological frameworks to targeted methods, tools, and indicators.

The first stage of the methodology focused on defining criteria to identify and select relevant frameworks, approaches, methodologies, methods, tools, and indicators. These instruments should help practitioners explore agricultural trade from a systems perspective and identify transition pathways toward sustainability.

In the second stage, various sources were consulted to identify and select relevant instruments based on the defined criteria. This included a review of academic and grey literature, as well as consultations with MATS partners.

In the third stage, the information gathered from each selected instrument was summarized and presented in fact sheets using descriptors. This preliminary version of the Toolbox was launched and shared with MATS partners in May 2022, informing the implementation of case studies, the analysis of linkages between agricultural trade, sustainability, and human well-being, and the derivation of transition pathways.

Once MATS activities were largely advanced and case studies finished, the Toolbox was revisited and updated to incorporate lessons learned throughout the project. In the fourth stage of the analysis, the Toolbox was updated by

considering the contributions of the instruments to the various stages of agricultural trade systemic analysis.

In the fifth stage, the updated Toolbox was shared with the 15 MATS case studies to gather feedback on the usefulness of each tool and stakeholder engagement level. This feedback was incorporated into the factsheets, resulting in the final version of the Toolbox.

Each of the methodology stages is described below.

3.1. Define search strategies to select relevant instruments for the Toolbox.

The main objective of the search was to find valuable instruments for developing future MATS activities. Three concurrent search strategies were applied.

- Using **keywords** related to agriculture, food production, trade, assessment, sustainability, and analysis. We chose not to restrict the search to the concepts associated with agricultural trade to better fit with MATS ambitions.
- Focusing on the **systemic nature** of MATS, ensuring instruments contribute to at least one of the following aspects: (i) Making sense of broader sustainability and human well-being issues related to agrifood trade; (ii) Exploring the dynamic behavior of food systems' dynamic; (iii) Recognizing the role of agency in how problematic situations in food systems are framed and addressed.
- Filtering tools by their **usefulness within MATS**, considering their contributions to identifying key leverage points that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agrifood trade on sustainability and human well-being – the main goal of MATS – through one or more of the

following processes: (i) assessment of the links between agricultural trade, agricultural and rural investments, environmental sustainability and human well-being; (ii) analysis of the role of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks given their impacts on SDGs and in respect of global agreements on environmental and climate change ; (iii) Visioning and backcasting processes to derive transition pathways for desirable changes in trade relations and formulate policy recommendations.

3.2. Identify and select relevant instruments for the Toolbox

Several sources were consulted to identify relevant instruments for the MATS Sustainable Trade Toolbox.

Considering the food systems perspective guiding this Deliverable, more than twenty food systems frameworks published between 2009 and 2021 were selected and consulted in search of relevant instruments for this Toolbox.

Afterward, we broadened the search focus by reviewing scientific and grey literature in search engines and databases using the keywords mentioned in the previous section.

Additionally, we consulted the [MATS Deliverable 2.2 "Synthesis of Model-Based Studies"](#) to include modeling methods and tools in the Toolbox.

A preliminary list of instruments was drawn up and shared with MATS consortium members for feedback, particularly those involved in assessing linkages between agricultural trade, sustainability, and human well-being (WP3); analyzing the role of institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks in the agricultural trade impacts on SDGs (WP4); and drawing transition pathways and policy recommendation towards sustainable agricultural trade (WP5). The information obtained was systematized in a unique database.

3.3. Develop instrument fact sheets to feed into the Toolbox

Fact sheets were created for each instrument, using descriptors to facilitate search and consultation. Each factsheet included:

- i. Name**
- ii. Type of instrument:** Categorized as (a) Tool, (b) Method, (c) Model, (d) Framework, and (e) Principles.
- iii. Topic:** This section shows the topic(s) the instrument addresses, linked to the dimensions of the Agricultural Trade Framework proposed in [MATS Deliverable 2.1 "SDG indicators for Assessing the Sustainability Impacts of Agricultural Trade"](#) to explore the agricultural trade systemically, highlighting its linkages with sustainability and human well-being.
- iv. Keywords:** The keywords are short descriptors for search facilitation. The keywords used can be understood in four types: (i) key features of the instrument; (ii) more information about the topic(s) addressed (e.g., for a tool addressing "human capital," a keyword could be "food security"); (iii) Contributions to a systemic analysis of the agricultural trade (e.g., "situation mapping," "forecast," "agency," "perspectives"); (iv) MATS activities and areas of interest (e.g., "food value chain," "political relations," "transition pathways," etc).
- v. Description:** It provides a high-level overview of the purpose and contributions of the instrument.
- vi. More info and source:** This section includes sources to consult for further information on the instrument, its use, and potential contributions.

vii. Application: This section includes references to scientific articles or reports with applications of the Toolbox instruments in agricultural trade, food systems, and sustainability.

The preliminary version of the Toolbox is included in [MATS Deliverable 2.3 "Sustainable Trade Toolbox."](#)

3.4. Review and update the Toolbox: Feedback and lessons learned throughout MATS.

When the MATS activities were largely advanced or fully developed, the Toolbox was reviewed and updated, incorporating lessons learned throughout MATS.

Descriptors were refined to enhance relevance for users analyzing complex issues related to agricultural trade, food systems, and sustainability within and beyond MATS.

The updated factsheets included:

i. Name

- ii. Type of instrument:** The categories of instruments were updated to reflect the instruments' diversity and facilitate user consultation.

Categories included "Guiding principles/ frameworks," "Analytical frameworks and indicators," "Secondary data review and analysis," "Stakeholder consultation tools," "Text/Content analysis," "Systems diagram," "Mapping instruments," "Analytical frameworks and indicators," "Economic analysis," "Environmental accounting tools," "Toolkit," "Statistics tools," "Quantitative model," "Mixed methods model," "Qualitative model," "Spatial model," "Exploratory and participatory learning methodology," and "Future-oriented planning tools."

- iii. Purpose:** This section, formerly "description," was updated to highlight the purpose of the instrument in a concise paragraph.

iv. Contributions to agrifood and sustainability-related analysis:

This section lists potential contributions in three main areas.

a) Data collection and analysis to make sense of the system.

- ✓ Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations.

b) Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- ✓ Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- ✓ Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.

- ✓ Exploring power structures and dynamics
- ✓ Exploring different scenarios to gain insights into the system's behavior and outcomes.

c) Identification of potential transition pathways and policy recommendations.

- ✓ Exploring different scenarios to gain insights into the system's behavior and outcomes.
- ✓ Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- ✓ Determine, explore, and question boundaries.
- ✓ Design transition pathways
- ✓ Provide political/ actionable recommendations.

Contributions fitting each instrument in the Toolbox were selected from the list above.

- v. Key literature:** This section includes sources for further information on the instrument, its use, and potential contributions.
- vi. Case studies/ examples of use:** This section includes references or links to scientific articles or official reports containing applications of each instrument related to agricultural trade, food systems, and sustainability. This section also includes MATS case study reports that offer practical information on the use and contributions of the instrument.

3.5. [Insights from practice: Feedback from MATS case studies.](#)

The updated Toolbox was shared with the 15 MATS case studies. Stakeholders provided feedback on four levels using a collaborative Excel document:

- i. **General feedback concerning the contributions of the instruments:** The list of instruments was shared with the MATS CS, linking each instrument to the analysis stages they contribute to: (a) Data collection and analysis, (b) Exploration of elements and linkages, and/or (c) Identification of transition pathways. Additionally, specific contributions to each analysis stage were described.

Based on the information provided, CS were asked to validate and suggest additions or modifications to these contributions.

- ii. **Validation of the instruments applied in the respective CS:** Instruments used in each MATS CS were identified from CS reports and other key deliverables in Work Package 3. Different tabs were prepared for each CS to review and complete the list of applied instruments.
- iii. **Specific feedback on the contributions/ usefulness of the instruments applied in the respective CS:** Once instruments were validated, CS leaders indicated each instrument's contribution level to each analysis stage (Table 1).

Contribution to each stage of the analysis
Greatly contributes
Highly contributes
Moderately contributes
Slightly contributes
Not sure

Table 1: Contributions of the instruments to each stage of the analysis.

- iv. **Specific feedback on the level of participation/ engagement of stakeholders in using instruments:** Lastly, CS leaders reflected on the level of involvement/ engagement of stakeholders during instrument application, ranging from using stakeholders as a source of information to engaging them as co-designers of solutions (Table 2).

Participation/ engagement of stakeholders
As a source of information
To provide feedback and validate findings
Actively involved in the analysis
Co-designers of solutions
Not involved

Table 2: Participation/ engagement of stakeholders

Feedback received was incorporated into the factsheets in blue boxes as practical findings. Notably, 13 out of 15 case studies participated in this validation process. Qualitative scales (Tables 1 and 2) were translated into numbers to average responses for instruments used across multiple case studies. The average response level is included in the respective factsheet as MATS findings. Note that the number of case studies applying each instrument varied widely – from 11 CS doing interviews and surveys to one CS using Measuring Distance to the SDG Targets, TCD (Trade Competitiveness Diagnostic Toolkit), ITC Standards map, or other instruments.

4. **Toolbox**

This section includes the factsheets for all the MATS Sustainable Trade Toolbox instruments, which have been revisited and updated based on the lessons learned and findings from the MATS project.

We trust this Toolbox to be useful for practitioners working in food systems, agricultural trade, and sustainable development. It offers a comprehensive range of instruments designed to help analyze, understand, and address complex issues.

Our goal is for the MATS Sustainable Trade Toolbox to have a lasting impact beyond the project's duration. To ensure its continued use, we plan to make it accessible on the MATS website as a searchable database for the factsheets presented in this section.

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1

Agent-based models

Mixed methods model

It can accommodate and simulate potential interactions between individual agents operating within dynamic environments. It represents individual agents in the system, each with specified initial conditions and a set of adaptive rules that govern their interaction with each other and with their environment.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems
- Identification of potential transition pathways

MATS findings

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Institute of Medicine, & National Research Council. (2015). A Framework for Assessing Effects of the Food System. Institute of Medicine and National Research Council of The National Academies.*
- *Kremmydas, D., et al. (2018). A review of Agent Based Modeling for agricultural policy evaluation. Agricultural Systems. 164. 95-106.*

MATS Case studies

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2

Aglink-Cosimo

Quantitative model

It is a recursive-dynamic, partial equilibrium model that is used to mainly replicate developments of the balances of the annual market and prices for the main agricultural commodities consumed, produced, and traded at the global level. It is used to create the OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook and policy scenario analysis. Aglink-Cosimo provides a comprehensive policy-specific and dynamic economic depiction of the standard temperate-zone commodities, as well as for cotton, vegetable oils, and rice.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Aglink-Cosimo Model Documentation - A partial equilibrium model of world agricultural markets.*
- *OECD/FAO (2015). OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2015. OECD Publishing, Paris.*

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3

AGMEMOD (Agricultural Member State Modelling)

Quantitative model

AGMEMOD is represented as a dynamic, econometric, multi-product partial equilibrium model in which a bottom-up approach is utilized. The respective approach captures the inherent heterogeneity of the agricultural systems existing across the EU, as well as ensures consistency across the country models through the adherence to agreed commodity model templates. AGMEMOD also promotes the significant comparison of the policy impact changes across the different Member States.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Van Leeuwen, M., et al. (2012). *AGMEMOD Model*. In *The Future of EU Agricultural Markets* by AGMEMOD (pp. 45-74). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Niemi, J., et al. (2005). *A tool to analyse the impact of policy changes on the agri-food sector of Finland*. In: Arfini, F. (ed.). *Modelling agricultural policies: state of the art and new challenges*. Parma: Monte Università Parma Editore, 609-629

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Agricultural Production Growth Models

Quantitative model

Agricultural production models examine the relationship between agricultural production and important inputs of production such as physical capital stock, labour, and land.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Ngalawa, H., & Derera, E. (2020). *Agricultural Production, Employment and Gender Vulnerability: Covid-19 Implications*. *African Journal of Governance & Development*, 9(1.1), 200-225

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5

Agricultural sustainability assessment framework

Analytical framework
& indicators

The developed agricultural sustainability indicators framework for the EU addresses SDG2 (aiming to end hunger, achieve food security, improve nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture) and SDG13 (calling for urgent action to combat climate change) and provides linkages between them and other policy areas. The selected relevant indicators are combined in the framework for harmonization of climate change and agriculture policies by selecting relevant policy actions for targeted indicators.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations.

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Streimikis, J., & Baležentis, T. (2020). Agricultural sustainability assessment framework integrating sustainable development goals and interlinked priorities of environmental, climate and agriculture policies. Sustainable Development, 28(6), 1702-1712*

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6

APSIM (Agricultural Production Systems SIMulator)

Quantitative model

Agricultural Production Systems sIMulator (APSIM), is a dynamic, process-based model aimed to simulating plant growth in a variety of biophysical and economic conditions.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- McCown, R. L., et al. (1996). APSIM: a novel software system for model development, model testing and simulation in agricultural systems research. *Agricultural Systems*, 50(3), 255-271.
- Keating, B. A., et al. (2003). An overview of APSIM, a model designed for farming systems simulation. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 18(3-4), 267-288.

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7

ARIES (Artificial Intelligence for Ecosystem Services)

Mixed methods
models

ARIES is a web-based model that assists rapid ecosystem service assessment and valuation (ESAV). It helps users discover, understand, and quantify environmental assets and the factors influencing their values, for specific geographic areas and based on user needs and priorities. ARIES encodes relevant ecological and socioeconomic knowledge to map ecosystem service provision, use, and benefit flows.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations.

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Integrated Modelling. (2021). Aries. An adaptive modelling technology.*
- *Villa, F., Ceroni, et al. (2009). ARIES (Artificial Intelligence for Ecosystem Services): a new tool for ecosystem services assessment, planning , and valuation . Aries, July 2014, 1–10.*

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8

ARIMA

Quantitative model

ARIMA model is one of the most useful techniques for future event forecasting. The model estimates a value in a response time series as a linear combination of its past values.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Box, G. E., & Jenkins, G. M. (1976). *Time series analysis: Forecasting and control* San Francisco. Calif: Holden-Day
- Kannan, S. & Karuppasamy, K.M. (2020). *Forecasting for Agricultural Production Using Arima Model. PalArch's Journal of Archaeology Of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(9), 5939-5949.
- Wang, K. C. (2021). *Reimagining the global food regimes for relational spaces. Area*, 53(4), 637-646

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9

ATLAS.ti.

Text/ Content analysis

ATLAS.ti is a powerful workbench for the qualitative analysis of larger bodies of textual, graphical, audio, and video data. It offers a variety of tools for accomplishing the tasks associated with any systematic approach to unstructured data, i.e., data that cannot be meaningfully analyzed by formal, statistical approaches.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

 MATS findings

MODERATELY
CONTRIBUTE

SLIGHTLY
CONTRIBUTE

AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- ATLAS. (2024). *Introduction - ATLAS.ti 24 Windows – User Manual*.
- Tolinggi, W. K., Salman, D., Rahmadanih, & Iswoyo, H. (2023). *Farmer regeneration and knowledge co-creation in the sustainability of coconut agribusiness in Gorontalo, Indonesia*. *Open Agriculture*, 8(1).

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10

Backcasting pathway builder tool

Future-oriented
planning tools

“Backcasting” works with a solution for a given setting to identify actionable steps towards having positive impact at some point in the future. The backcasting pathway builder tool meant to serve as a starting point to help develop concrete, actionable steps to achieve the vision of a solution for a specific context. The end result of the backcasting process is a clearly defined “pathway-to-impact” map that outlines the what, when and how of moving an idea towards a desired impact, and also who to work with along the way.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *IFSS Portal. (2021). Moving to action. Backcasting Tool.*
- *Carlsson-Kanyama, A., et al. (2008). Participative backcasting: A tool for involving stakeholders in local sustainability planning. Futures, 40(1), 34–46.*

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B-INTACT (The Biodiversity Integrated Assessment and Computation Tool)

Environmental
accounting tools

The B-INTACT aims to provide a thorough biodiversity assessment of project-level activities in the Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) sector to help making informed decisions. Through a quantitative approach, B-INTACT considers a set of relationships for anthropogenic impacts on biodiversity from land use changes, habitat fragmentation, infrastructure and human encroachment, expressed in the mean species abundance (MSA) metric. Non-quantifiable impacts to biodiversity from project activities are assessed with a qualitative appraisal. The tool aims to quantify the biodiversity impact of various investments at project and policy-level using globally recognized environmental assessment methodologies.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations.

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- FAO. (2022a). *Economic and Policy Analysis of Climate Change. The Biodiversity Integrated Assessment and Computation Tool (B-INTACT)*.
- Basset-Mens, C., et al. (2021). *Life Cycle Assessment of agri-food systems. An operational guide dedicated to emerging and developing economies*, Éditions Quae, Versailles, 210 p.

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12

Calibrated programming models

Quantitative model

Calibrated programming models cover only economy and environmental dimensions. Calibration methods for models of agricultural production and water (e.g., SWAP) provide a tool for regional water management and policy as well as a framework for integrating many aspects of regional water and agricultural management.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Howitt, R. E. (1995). *Positive mathematical programming*. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 77(2), 329-342.
- Graveline, N. (2016). *Economic calibrated models for water allocation in agricultural production: A review*. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 81, 12–25.

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13

CAPRI (Common Agricultural Policy Regionalized Impact)

Quantitative model

CAPRI modelling framework is considered to be a global static partial equilibrium model regarding the agricultural and primary processing sectors, used to assess the effects of CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) instruments at the EU or Member State level, as well as at sub-national level (Britz and Witzke, 2014). CAPRI model is mainly used for ex-ante impact assessment of environmental, agricultural, and trade policy options, thence supporting decision making concerning the agricultural sector.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Britz, W., & Witzke, P. (2014). *CAPRI Model Documentation 2014*.
- Barreiro Hurlé, J., et al. (2021). *Modelling environmental and climate ambition in the agricultural sector with the CAPRI model (No. JRC121368)*. Joint Research Centre (Seville site)

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CARD Model

Quantitative model

It is a system of econometric, partial equilibrium, non-spatial models for global agriculture, which covers all major temperate crops, sugar, biofuels, dairy, livestock, and meat products for all major producing and consuming regions and countries. The CARD model has been used in various studies to analyze the impact of policies and shocks on agricultural markets. The CARD modelling system is run to generate a baseline, which establishes 10-year projections by country and by crop for production, consumption, prices, and trade. Once the baseline is established, certain components of the modelling system are modified to simulate a specific scenario and the system is rerun to obtain a new market equilibrium for all commodity markets in the model.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Searchinger, T., et al. (2008). Use of US croplands for biofuels increases greenhouse gases through emissions from land-use change. *Science*, 319(5867), 1238-1240.
- Hayes, D., et al. (2009). Biofuels: potential production capacity, effects on grain and livestock sectors, and implications for food prices and consumers. *Journal of Agricultural and Applied Economics*, 41(2), 465-491.

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15

Causal Loop diagram

To reach a higher/ more systemic level of understanding by mapping the structure – variables and relationships - responsible for the systems’ patterns of behaviour and dynamics over time.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Designing transition pathways.
 - Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

MATS findings

HIGHLY CONTRIBUTE

HIGHLY CONTRIBUTE

GREATLY CONTRIBUTE

- AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION
- TO PROVIDE FEEDBACK AND VALIDATE FINDING

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Williams, B., & Hummelbrunner, R. (2009). *Systems concepts in action: a practitioner’s toolkit*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press. pp. 31-44
- Inam, A., et al. (2015). *Using causal loop diagrams for the initialization of stakeholder engagement in soil salinity management in agricultural watersheds in developing countries: A case study in the Rechna Doab watershed, Pakistan*. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 152, 251–267.

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CBA (Cost Benefit Analysis)

Economic analysis

CBA is a systematic process for calculating and comparing benefits and costs of a given policy or project, based on assigning a monetary value to all the activities associated with the project (either as input or output). This approach generally compares the total investment and other costs required for the implementation of the project. CBA techniques are commonly used to evaluate the feasibility and profitability of business strategies and private and public projects, as well as public policy interventions. CBA helps make clear the total costs of an intervention, as well as the benefits generated.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
 - Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

MATS findings

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- IFAD. (2015). *Basic concepts and rationale. IFAD'S Internal Guideliness. Economic and Financial Analysis of rural investment projects.*
- Sharma, A. (2021). *Cost-benefit analysis rules for the foodservice system. Journal of Hospitality Financial Management, 29(1), 14–21.*
- Miklyaev, M., et al. (2021). *Sustainability of agricultural crop policies in Rwanda: An integrated cost–benefit analysis. Sustainability (Switzerland), 13(1), 1–22.*

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CEA (Cost-Effectiveness Analysis)

Economic analysis

Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) compares the relative costs and outcomes (non-monetary effects) of two or more courses of action. It is narrower than a Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) and excludes any valuation of benefits, focusing instead on the costs of attaining a given target.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *TEEB. (2018). Chapter 7. Teebagrifood Methodology: An overview of evaluation and valuation methods and tools.*
- *Verguet, S., et al. (2016). Extended Cost-Effectiveness Analysis for Health Policy Assessment: A Tutorial. Pharmacoeconomics, 34(9), 913–923.*
- *Basu, S., et al. (2013). Nutritional policy changes in the supplemental nutrition assistance program: A microsimulation and cost-effectiveness analysis. Medical Decision Making, 33(7), 937–948.*

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CGE Models (Computable General Equilibrium)

Quantitative model

It simulates an economy with multiple goods produced by various sectors, describing their interactions. They account for producers' profit-maximizing and consumers' utility-maximizing behaviors, as well as macroeconomic factors like GDP changes, aggregate saving and investment, government revenues and spending, and trade balance. CGE models require extensive databases.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Viana, J. H., de Moraes, M. M. A., & Araujo Jr, I. T. (2018). *Impacts of a Reduction in Water Availability for Agriculture in Brazil*. Available at SSRN 3195243.
- Mbanda, V., & Ncube, S. (2021). *CGE Analysis of Rural Economic Development through Agriculture Policy in South Africa: A Focus on*

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19

Controversy scan

Guiding principles

Controversy scan is a systematic analysis of existing debates in a specific field. It identifies and examines different opinions, arguments, and evidence, aiming to map the full discussion, understand divergent positions, and highlight areas of consensus and disagreement.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.

MATS findings

GREATLY CONTRIBUTE

SLIGHTLY CONTRIBUTE

HIGHLY CONTRIBUTE

AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

MATS Case studies

- Abdullahi-Idiagbon (2013). Discourse Analysis – A critical appraisal of concepts and controversies. ABUAD Journal of the Humanities Vo. 1 N°1 pp1-9

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CROPWAT (Water Supply and Water Requirements)

Environmental
accounting tools

CROPWAT is a decision support tool. It facilitates the calculation of crop water requirements and irrigation requirements based on soil, climate and crop data. It informs the development of irrigation schedules for different management conditions and the calculation of required water supply for varying crop patterns.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *TEEB. (2018). Chapter 7. Teebagrifood Methodology: An overview of evaluation and valuation methods and tools.*
- *Bouraima, A. K., et al. (2015). Irrigation water requirements of rice using Cropwat model in Northern Benin. International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering, 8(2), 58–64.*

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DCGE (Dynamic Computable General Equilibrium)

Quantitative model

Dynamic Computable General Equilibrium (DCGE) model explores the association between domestic and international markets by assuming imperfect price-sensitive substitution between domestic production and imports.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Sánchez Chóliz, J., & Sarasa, C. (2019). *Uncertainty in irrigation technology: insights from a CGE approach*. *Water*, 11(3), 617.
- Solomon, R., Simane, B., & Zaitchik, B. F. (2021). *The impact of climate change on agriculture production in Ethiopia: application of a dynamic computable general equilibrium model*. *American Journal of Climate Change*, 10(1), 32-50

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It is an iterative process that involves sending various rounds of questions to a selected group of experts on a particular subject. Responses to one round are summarized and used to inform the next round of questions, seeking to identify agreement and disagreements among participants and generating insights about the topic.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
- Exploring power structures and dynamics

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations
- Determine, explore, and question boundaries.
- Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Global Alliance for improved Nutrition, G. A. for improved. (2021). DELPHI TOOLKIT A tool to surface and assess innovative solutions (Issue May).*
- *Mullender, S. M., et al. (2020). A delphi-style approach for developing an integrated food/non-food system sustainability assessment tool. Environmental Impact Assessment Review, 84.*

Dynamic CGE-Water modelling framework is a multi-sector, multi-region, recursively dynamic modelling approach. It works water stress scenarios, with respect to the role of sustainable water supplies with regard to agricultural and additional sectors.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Hertel, T. W. (1997). *Global Trade Analysis: Modeling and Applications*. Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press. 1997.
- Zeshan, M., & Shakeel, M. (2021). *Water Crisis in Pakistan: A Dynamic CGE-Water Model*

EX-Ante Carbon-balance Tool (EX-ACT)

Environmental
accounting tools

EX-ACT is based on the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) methodology for greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions inventories. EX-ACT provides its users a consistent way of estimating and tracking the outcomes of agricultural interventions on GHG emissions. EX-ACT is the only GHG accounting tool to cover the entire agricultural sector including Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU,) inland and coastal wetlands, fisheries and aquaculture, agricultural inputs and infrastructure.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
 - Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- FAO. (2022b). *Economic and Policy Analysis of Climate Change. The EX-Ante Carbon-balance Tool (EX-ACT)*.
- FAO. (2019). *EX-Ante Carbon-balance Tool | EX-ACT: Mainstreaming greenhouse gas accounting into agricultural investments and policies*.

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EX-Ante Carbon-balance Tool for value chains (EX-ACT VC)

Environmental
accounting tools

EX-ACT VC is a quantitative multi-appraisal tool that aims to support policymakers in identifying greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions along an agri-food value chain. It analyses GHG fluxes from farm-gate-to-shelf, as well as potential entry points for socio-economic improvements at each stage of the value chain, allowing the projects and policies for low carbon value chains.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations.

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- FAO. (2022c). *Economic and Policy Analysis of Climate Change. The EX-Ante Carbon-balance Tool for value chains (EX-ACT VC)*.
- FAO. (2020). *EX-Ante Carbon-balance Tool for value chains: Assessing environmental and socio-economic potential of agri-food value chains*.

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FAO framework on ending child labour in agriculture

Guiding principles/
frameworks

The purpose of the FAO's framework is to guide the Organization in the integration of measures addressing child labour within programmes and initiatives at global, regional and country levels. The framework is aimed to be used by FAO, but others outside the organization are invited to use it. The framework provides definitions and visions on child labour, along with guiding principles, key areas of work, and strategies to work on ending child labour.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- FAO. 2020. *FAO framework on ending child labour in agriculture*. Rome.

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FAPDA (Food And Agriculture Policy Decision Analysis)

Secondary data
review and analysis

Food And Agriculture Policy Decision Analysis (FAPDA) is a web-based platform gathering information on food and agriculture policy decisions since 2007 from more than 80 countries (5000+ policies registered). The tool allows users to directly access and retrieve information by country or region, date or type of policy.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *FAO. (2022d). Fapda - Food And Agriculture Policy Decision Analysis Tool.*
- *Maetz, M., Aguirre, M., Kim, S., Matinroshan, Y., Pangrazio, G., & Pernechele, V. (2011). Food and agricultural policy trends after the 2008 food security crisis. 44.*

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Feminist Principles to Program, Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability and Learning

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Examples and lessons learned to illustrate how the Oxfam International Feminist Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability and Learning (MEAL) Principles has been used in the design and practices of MEAL systems.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Wakefield, S., & Koerppen, D. (2017). *Applying Feminist Principles to program monitoring, evaluation, accountability and learning*. Oxfam Discussion Paper.

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Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)

Stakeholders' consultation tools

Focus group discussions involve small groups of people with specialized knowledge or interest in a topic to explore their perceptions and attitudes. They can be used at any stage of a project or program, from design to evaluation.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
- Exploring power structures and dynamics

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations
- Determine, explore, and question boundaries.
- Designing transition pathways.

MATS findings

- AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION
- CODESIGNERS OF SOLUTIONS
- TO PROVIDE FEEDBACK AND VALIDATE FINDING

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- USAID (2011). *Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Tips: Conducting focus group interviews*. Number 10.
- Mashingaidze, N., et al. (2020). *Participatory Exploration of the Heterogeneity in Household Socioeconomic, Food, and Nutrition Security Status for the Identification of Nutrition-Sensitive Interventions in the Rwandan Highlands*. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 4, 519928.

MATS Case studies

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Information and decision-support tools to strengthen the ability of policymakers, food policy experts, and researchers to respond quickly to dynamic developments in the world food system.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
- Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Food Security Portal. (2022). Food Policy Analysis Tools.*
- *Louhichi, K., & Gomez y Paloma, S. (2014). A farm household model for agri-food policy analysis in developing countries: Application to smallholder farmers in Sierra Leone. Food Policy, 45, 1–13.*

Exploratory and
participatory learning
methodology

Force Field Analysis, is a widely used tool to inform decision making, particularly with regards to managing change. The method can be used to gain a comprehensive overview and assess the sources and strengths of all different forces acting on a potential organizational issue or intervention.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Designing transition pathways.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *MSP Guide. (2022a). Force Field Analysis. Tool 16. .*
- *Schwering, R. E. (2003). Focusing leadership through force field analysis: new variations on a venerable planning tool. Leadership & Organization Development Journal, 24(7), 361–370.*

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Exploratory and
participatory learning
methodology

This tool aims to help reflecting on different expressions and faces of power in different stages of a Multistakeholder Partnership. It helps to generate conversations among stakeholders when strategies for change are discussed, hence helping to understand power dynamics.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
 - Exploring power structures and dynamics.
- Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *MSP Guide. (2022). Forms of Power. Tool 27.*

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FPA (Flower Pollinated Algorithm)

Quantitative model

Flower Pollinated Algorithm (FPA) is an optimal crop allocation model utilized to solve diverse types of optimization matters, with its algorithm based on total land available, planting costs, crops expected yield, and market prices.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Yang, X. S. (2012, September). Flower pollination algorithm for global optimization. In *International Conference on Unconventional Computing and Natural Computation* (pp. 240-249). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Ejeji, C. N., & Akinsunmade, A. E. (2020). Agricultural Model for Allocation of Crops Using Pollination Intelligence Method. *Applied Computational Intelligence and Soft Computing*, 2020.

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Fuzzy Cognitive Maps

Qualitative model

Semiquantitative models that represent the behaviour of complex systems based on people's perceptions. It aggregates stakeholders/ expert knowledge into a standardized format, thus allowing a broad range of knowledge types to be in-regrated and communicated. According to Gray et al. (2015), FCM van be used to understand change and transition in Socio-Environmental Systems by (1) sharing knowledge to define the state space of a given system, (2) analyzing the structure of a system, (3) analyzing system's functions through scenarios, and (4) evaluating how changes to structural configurations may relate to movement toward or away from desirable and undesirable future trajectories.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Designing transition pathways.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Gray, S. A, et al. (2015). Using fuzzy cognitive mapping as a participatory approach to analyze change, preferred states, and perceived resilience of social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society*.
- Halbe, J., & Adamowski, J. (2019). Modeling sustainability visions: A case study of multi-scale food systems in Southwestern Ontario. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 231, 1028–1047.

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GEM (Green Economy Model)

Quantitative model

GEM is an integrated assessment model used to analyze the impacts of sustainable development-oriented policies across sectors and actors over time, and if integrated with spatial modelling, space. At the core of the module are land use for crop production and land productivity as well as the total livestock herd. GEM forecasts agriculture land use and livestock herd based on total population, productivity, and climate-related variables. Forecasts are usually aligned with relevant development plans and/or validated by relevant project stakeholders.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- UNEP (2011). *Towards a Green Economy: Pathways to Sustainable Development and Poverty Eradication*. Nairobi, United Nations Environment Programme.
- GoE (2021). *Updated Nationally Determined Contribution - Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia*. Government of Ethiopia.

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GEM-E3 (General Equilibrium Model for Economy, Energy, and Environment)

Quantitative model

GEM-E3 is a recursive dynamic CGE model, multi-regional and multi-sectoral that is mainly used for policy analyses and impact evaluations on the three E's. The creators (Capros et al., 2013) aimed to cover the topic of sustainable economic growth and to support the study of associated policy matters.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Capros, P., et al. (2013). *GEM-E3 model documentation*. JRC Scientific and Policy Reports, 26034.
- Paroussos, L., Fragkiadakis, K., & Fragkos, P. (2020). *Macro-economic analysis of green growth policies: the role of finance and technical progress in Italian green growth*. *Climatic Change*, 160(4), 591-608.

[Table of content](#)

GIS is a technological tool that captures, manages, and helps to analyse all forms of geographic reference data and facilitate informed decision making. It's an information system which helps integrate and present geographical data as per specific project requirements. Use of the GIS tool is increasing in building (schedule management, supply footprint, logistics, etc.), O&M (energy, space management, waste management etc.), and recycling portions of the life cycle.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Khandelwal, A. (2012). *Using GIS to advance sustainability. Sustainability Outlook.*
- Gimpel, A., Stelzenmüller, V., Töpsch, S., Galparsoro, I., Gubbins, M., Miller, D., Murillas, A., Murray, A. G., Pınarbaşı, K., Roca, G., & Watret, R. (2018). *A GIS-based tool for an integrated assessment of spatial planning trade-offs with aquaculture. Science of the Total Environment, 627, 1644–1655.*

GLOBIOM (Global Biosphere Management Model)

Quantitative model

GLOBIOM is a global, recursively dynamic, partial equilibrium model used to investigate the various trade-offs and synergies around land use and ecosystem services. It uses extensive socioeconomic and geospatial data to capture the numerous interrelationships between diverse systems engaged in the provision of agriculture and forestry products. It includes the 18 most important crops in the world, as well as a variety of livestock production operations, forestry commodities, first and second-generation bioenergy, and water.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Takayama, T., & Judge, G. G. (1964). An interregional activity analysis model for the agricultural sector. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 46(2), 349- 365.
- McCarl, B. A., & Spreen, T. H. (1980). Price endogenous mathematical programming as a tool for sector analysis. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 62(1), 87-102.

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Quantitative model

GTAP model is a global, general equilibrium, comparative static model, based on an input-output accounting framework that is complete, in the sense that all sources and uses of each economic good are accounted for, as are all inputs into production. The standard GTAP model does assume perfectly competitive markets and constant returns to scale.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Hertel, T. W., & Tsigas M. E. (1997). *Structure of GTAP*. In *Global Trade Analysis: Modeling and Applications*, edited by T. W. Hertel, 9–71. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Corong, E. L., Hertel, T. W., McDougall, R., Tsigas, M. E., & van der Mensbrugge, D. (2017). *The standard GTAP model, version 7*. *Journal of Global Economic Analysis*, 2(1), 1-119.

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GTAP model extensions

Quantitative model

Standard GTAP model has been frequently modified to become more suitable for policy analysis. In particular, the following six modifications of the standard GTAP model are considered for policy analysis: (1) GTAP-AGR examines agricultural policy reforms; (2) GTAP-POV evaluates the consequences of agricultural policy reforms on poverty in the world's poorest countries; (3) MyGTAP evaluates the distributional impacts of policy applications; (4) a detailed, partial equilibrium model of the dairy sector, which allows for sophisticated analysis of tariff-line expansion; (5) GTAP-E (Burniaux and Truong, 2002) represents energy demands across the economy and binds these to GHG emissions, focusing on the potential for substituting fossil fuels and between those fuels and other sources of energy and capital/labour; (6) GTAP-IRIS (Francois, 1998) has a variety of market structures, such as monopolistic competition or Cournot oligopoly with scale economies.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Keeney, R., & Hertel, T. (2005). *GTAP-AGR: A framework for assessing the implications of multilateral changes in agricultural policies. Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP), Department of Agricultural Economics, Purdue University, West Lafayette, IN, GTAP Technical Paper No. 24.*
- Beckman, J., Estrades, C., & Aguiar, A. (2019). *Export taxes, food prices and poverty: a global CGE evaluation. Food Security, 11(1), 233-247.*

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GTEM-C (The Global Trade and Environment Model)

Quantitative model

GTEM-C is a dynamic general equilibrium and economy-wide model, capable of projecting trajectories for globally-traded commodities (including agricultural products) and builds upon the global trade and economic core of the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) database. Natural resources, land, and labour are endogenous variables in GTEM-C.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Cai, Y., et al. (2015). *A hybrid energy economy model for global integrated assessment of climate change, carbon mitigation and energy transformation*. *Applied Energy*, 148, 381-395.
- Porfirio, L. L., Newth, D., Finnigan, J. J., & Cai, Y. (2018). *Economic shifts in agricultural production and trade due to climate change*. *Palgrave Communications*, 4(1), 1-9.

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It presents ideas, strategies and tools to integrate gender, or create gender-focused works, across themes and issues. It includes methodological guidance to: (i) conduct a gender analysis of context & situation; (ii) conduct a gender power analysis; (iii) design a theory of change; (iv) formulate objectives with a gender lens; (v) design the strategy & tactics; (vi) actualize your influencing.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
- Exploring power structures and dynamics

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations
- Determine, explore, and question boundaries.
- Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Blackwell, R., & America, O. (n.d.). *Oxfam's Guide to Feminist Influencing*.
- Savani, M. M., & Stewart, A. (2019). *Making market systems work for women dairy farmers in Bangladesh: A final evaluation of Oxfam's Gendered Enterprise and Markets programme in Bangladesh. December 1–35.*

Gender analysis is part and parcel of social analysis and the study of social diversity. It provides a focused examination of the differences in the asset bases, livelihood strategies and vulnerabilities between women and men, as well as the reasons for and implications of these differences.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring power structures and dynamics.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2022). Investment Learning Platform (ILP).*
- *International Fund for Agricultural Development. (2017). Community-led value chain development for gender justice and pro-poor wealth creation. 1–4.*
- *Papers, G. D. (2016). Identifying gender inequalities and possibilities for change in shrimp value chains in indonesia and vietnam. Oxfam.*

Guidelines for integrating gender in research planning

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Guidelines document to integrate a clear and strong gender analysis when planning research. It includes a rubric to identify how integrated gender is in your research.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring power structures and dynamics.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Parvez Butt, A., Jayasinghe, N., & Zaaroura, M. (2019). *Integrating Gender in Research Planning*.
- Njuki, J., Waithanji, E., Bagalwa, N., & Kariuki, J. (2013). *Guidelines on integrating gender in livestock projects and programs*. ILRI Project Report.

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Handbook for monitoring and evaluation of child labour in agriculture

Guiding principles/
frameworks

The Handbook offers guidance and tools for assessing the impacts of agricultural and food security programmes and projects on child labour in family-based agriculture. The handbook is structured around 3 parts: an analysis of child labour in agriculture, monitoring and evaluation guidance on ending child labour, and a toolkit along with templates for working on ending child labour.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *FAO (2015). Handbook for monitoring and evaluation of child labour in agriculture. Measuring the impacts of agricultural and food security programmes on child labour in family-based agriculture. Rome, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.*

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Horizon Scanning

Future-oriented
planning tools

Horizon scanning is a method of identifying emerging changes at an early stage and assessing how relevant they are for current issues, goals or strategic decisions. Horizon scanning involves the search, evaluation and preparation of signals for current and future developments. Signals are data or indications that may be weak or strong, hidden or already known. If signals for developments stabilize over time, they can establish a medium- to long-term trend or megatrend. Several such trends are bundled in the so-called "sense-making" phase of horizon scanning to form future themes with possible effects, opportunities and risks.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Geurts, A., et al. (2022). *New perspectives for data-supported foresight: The hybrid AI-expert approach. Futures & foresight science*, 4(1).
- Institute of Risk Management. n.d. *Horizon Scanning: A Practitioner's Guide*.
- Glaros, A., et al. (2022). *Horizon scanning and review of the impact of five food and food production models for the global food system in 2050. Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 119(November 2021), 550–564.

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Human Rights-based approach to data

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Set of principles, recommendations and good practices that provide guidance and elements of a common understanding on a Human Rights-Based Approach to Data (HRBAD), with a focus on issues of data collection and disaggregation.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *United Nations Human Rights. (2022). A Human Rights-Based Approach To Data Leaving No One Behind in the 2030. .*

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HRIA (Human Rights Impact Assessment)

Guiding principles/
frameworks

HRIA is an instrument for examining policies, legislation, programs and projects to identify and measure their effects on human rights. HRIA's essential purpose is to help prevent harmful effects of the action, while maximizing positive effects. HRIA can be useful, in cases where the human rights implications of a proposed policy or project are not clear at the beginning and enhance accountability for impacts on human rights.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Alternative, G. (2020). Human rights impact assessment toolkit.*
- *FIDH, CEHPRODEC, & FUPNAPIB. (2017). Endangered Protected Areas and Water Resources in Honduras. The case of the Cuyamel II Hydroelectric Dam Project in San Francisco, Atlántida.*
- *FDIH, PASO, & CCAJAR. (2016). The Human Cost of Oil: A Human Rights Impact Assessment on the Activities of Pacific Exploration & Production Corp. in Puerto Gaitan.*

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Human Rights Indicators

Analytical framework
& indicators

Guide covering the conceptual, methodological, and empirical aspects of the approach underlying the identification of context-sensitive indicators to promote and monitor the implementation of human rights. It outlines a framework for building the capacity of human rights monitoring systems and facilitating the use of appropriate tools in policy-making, its implementation and monitoring.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *United Nations Human Rights. (2012). Human right indicators: A Guide to Measurement.*
- *Tomaševski, K. (1984). "Human Rights Indicators: The Right to Food as a Test Case". In The Right to Food. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill | Nijhoff.*

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IAMs (Integrated Assessment Models)

Mixed methods
model

IAMs are designed to examine issues related to the future development of environmental and sustainability topics. Such models examine the interactions between human activities (such as energy use and agriculture) and environmental factors such as land cover and climate systems. They are used to answer policy questions. Integrated assessment models estimate what possible scenarios look like and they do not provide predictions for the future.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Hasegawa, T., et al. (2018). Risk of increased food insecurity under stringent global climate change mitigation policy. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(8), 699-703.
- Searchinger, Tet al. (2015). Do biofuel policies seek to cut emissions by cutting food?. *Science*, 347(6229), 1420-1422.

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IBAT (Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool)

Secondary data
review and analysis

IBAT provides a basic risk screening on biodiversity. It draws together information on globally recognized biodiversity information drawn from a number of IUCN's Knowledge Products: IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, Key Biodiversity Areas (priority sites for conservation) and Protected Planet/The World Database on Protected Areas (covering nationally and internationally recognized sites, including IUCN management categories I–VI, Ramsar Wetlands of International Importance and World Heritage sites). Through an interactive mapping tool, decision-makers are able to easily access and use this up-to-date information to identify biodiversity risks and opportunities within or close to a project boundary.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- IBAT. (2022). *Sample Downloads. Reports.*
- Nygård, H., Murray, C., Andersen, J. H., Martin, G., Torn, K., & Korpinen, S. (2018). BEAT 3.0 – a Tool for Integrated Biodiversity Assessments. *Journal of Open Research Software*, 6, 1–5.

[Table of content](#)

IDRISI is a land use model to plot out optimal physical placement of economic activities, human settlements and other land uses. Practically, through the identification of trends (e.g. for population) and/or the use of assumptions for future land use change (e.g. land use per person). This model generate future land cover maps that optimize placement in space.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations.

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *TEEB. (2018). Chapter 7. Teebagrifood Methodology: An overview of evaluation and valuation methods and tools.*
- *Mishra, V., Rai, P., & Mohan, K. (2014). Prediction of land use changes based on land change modeler (LCM) using remote sensing: A case study of Muzaffarpur (Bihar), India. Journal of the Geographical Institute Jovan Cvijic, SASA, 64(1), 111–127.*

IMPACT (The International Model for Policy Analysis of Agricultural Commodities and Trade)

Quantitative model

IMPACT is a model that tests the connection of essential food commodities and food demand with security on a national level under the circumstances of future alterations of related factors. It is an integrated modelling system linked mainly to core partial equilibrium, multimarket model and is focused on the agriculture sector considering trade, global production, demand, and prices for agricultural commodities. This model provides policymakers and researchers with the flexibility to examine and compare the effects of changes in socioeconomic trends, biophysical systems, policies, and technologies.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Robinson, S., et al. (2015). *The international model for policy analysis of agricultural commodities and trade (IMPACT): model description for version 3*. Environment and Production Technology Division of IFPRI.
- Waithaka, M., Nelson, G. C., Thomas, T. S., & Kyotalimye, M. (Eds.). (2013). *East African agriculture and climate change: A comprehensive analysis*. Washington, DC: International Food Policy Research Institute.

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Making an Importance versus Influence Matrix helps to map out stakeholders and their relation to the issue. It generates insights on the importance and influence of each stakeholder. With this information, it becomes possible to develop a specific approach and strategy for the identified stakeholders.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *MSP Guide. (2022e). Stakeholder Analysis. Tool 12.*
- *Xu, W., Zhou, C., Cao, A., & Luo, M. (2016). Understanding the mechanism of food waste management by using stakeholder analysis and social network model: An industrial ecology perspective. Ecological Modelling, 337, 63–72.*

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Integrating Gender Issues into Agricultural Chains (INGIA-VC framework)

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Five-step process for identifying and evaluating gender-based constraints within agricultural value chains with tools and worksheets for implementing the process.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring power structures and dynamics.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Gender Platform. (2022). Gender Platform.*
- *Rubin, Deborah (Cultural Practice LLC), Cristina Manfre (dTS) Barrett, and Kara (dTS) Nichols. 2009. Promoting Gender Equitable Opportunities in Agricultural Value Chains; Promoting Gender Equitable Opportunities in Agricultural Value Chains: A Handbook. Washington, DC: USAID.*

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Interviews

Stakeholders' consultation tools

A semi-structured interview is one of the most effective tools for systematically gathering qualitative and quantitative data. This is a method which allows you to ask predetermined questions, determined, perhaps, by the theoretical framework or theory of change underpinning the project, or by your research hypothesis. It is also one which keeps questions open-ended, to gain a comprehensive view of surrounding information.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
- Exploring power structures and dynamics

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations
- Determine, explore, and question boundaries.
- Designing transition pathways.

MATS findings

GREATLY CONTRIBUTE

HIGHLY CONTRIBUTE

MODERATELY CONTRIBUTE

- AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION
- CODESIGNERS OF SOLUTIONS
- TO PROVIDE FEEDBACK AND VALIDATE FINDING

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Biden, A. (2022). *How to Conduct and Analyze Semi-Structured Interviews*. Evalcareers..
- Bloemhof, J. M., van der Vorst, J. G. A. J., Bastl, M., & Allaoui, H. (2015). *Sustainability assessment of food chain logistics*. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 18(2), 101–117.

MATS Case studies

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InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Environmental Services and Trade Offs)

Mixed methods
model

InVEST quantifies and maps environmental services and supports (if required) their economic valuation, allowing defining how changes in the structure and the functioning of ecosystems can affect the flows and values of ecosystem services across a landscape.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Stanford University. (2022). Natural Capital Project. InVest.*
- *Nelson, E., et al. (2009). Modeling multiple ecosystem services, biodiversity conservation, commodity production, and tradeoffs at landscape scales. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 7(1), 4–11.*
- *Hamel, P., et al. (2021). Mapping the benefits of nature in cities with the InVEST software. *Npj Urban Sustainability*, 1(1).*

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IPC Population Tracking Tool

Secondary data
review and analysis

Integrated Food Security Phase Classification (IPC) Population Tracking Tool is an online platform that gives the public access to population data from more than 30 different countries. It allows users to download resource data for offline IPC analyses since 2017. All national population figures are based on official country population estimates. IPC estimates are those published in country IPC reports.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- IPC Global Platform. (2022). *The IPC Population Tracking Tool*.
- Fredriksen, A. (2016). *Crisis in 'a normal bad year': Spaces of humanitarian emergency, the Integrated Food Security Phase Classification scale and the Somali famine of 2011*. *Environment and Planning A*, 48(1), 40–57.

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iSDG (Integrated Sustainable Development Goal)

Mixed methods
model

iSDG is a Systems Dynamics model intended to assist policymakers and policy planners to determine efficient pathways toward the SDGs. The iSDG model simulates the fundamental trends for SDGs until 2030 under a business-as-usual scenario and supports the analysis of relevant alternative scenarios. The model also traces the trends beyond the SDGs' time span all the way up to 2050.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Arquitt, S. (2020). *Industry note: Seeing through the SDG maze—the iSDG model, a simulation-based tool to aid SDG planners*. *International Journal of Agriculture Innovation, Technology and Globalisation*, 1(4), 315-322.
- Pedercini, M., Zuellich, G., Dianati, K., & Arquitt, S. (2018). *Toward achieving sustainable development goals in Ivory Coast: Simulating pathways to sustainable development*. *Sustainable Development*, 26(6), 588-595.

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ITC Standards map

 Secondary data review and analysis

ITC's Standards Map is a free online tool to easily find information and discover trends on standards for environmental protection, labour rights, business ethics, due diligence and traceability, among others.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

 MATS findings

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
 - Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
- Identification of potential transition pathways

HIGHLY
CONTRIBUTE

Stakeholders engagement:

NOT INVOLVED

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- ITC. (2024). *Standards Map* | ITC. *The world's largest database for sustainability standards.*
- Sonderegger, G., Heinemann, A., Diogo, V., & Oberlack, C. (2022). *Governing spillovers of agricultural land use through voluntary sustainability standards: A coverage analysis of sustainability requirements.* *Earth System Governance*, 14, 100158.

MATS Case studies

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KSNL (Criteria for Sustainable Farming)

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Criteria for Sustainable Farming (KSNL) focuses on analysis and certification for the sustainable farm-level crop, livestock, and bioenergy production to identify deficiencies of different sustainable agriculture criteria and advise farmers.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Breitschuh, G., et al. (2008). *Kriteriensystem nachhaltige Landwirtschaft (KSNL)*. KTBL-Schrift 466, Kuratorium für Technik und Bauwesen in der Landwirtschaft e.V. (KTBL), Darmstadt, Germany.
- Zapt, R., & Doluschitz, R. (2008). *Assessment of sustainability - common requirements and comparative evaluation of the systems RISE, KSNL and the "DLG certification system for sustainable agriculture."* 86(3), 357–540.

Table of content

The LandAssess Tool is a risk assessment and management framework. It provides a clear and simple set of checklists that generate a report to help agricultural companies assess and manage how they respect land rights.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Landesa (2022). LANDASSESS TOOL.

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LCA (Life Cycle Assessment)

Secondary data
review and analysis

LCA is defined as: “a systematic set of procedures for compiling and examining the inputs and outputs of materials and energy and the associated environmental impacts directly attributable to the functioning of a product or service system throughout its life cycle” (IOS 2016). LCA examines physical impacts across the value chain; it can also be viewed as “a tool for the assessment of environmental loadings of entire life cycle processes related to a production system, covering all the processes, activities and resources used” (Mogensen et al. 2012).

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *TEEB. (2018). Chapter 7. Teebagrifood Methodology: An overview of evaluation and valuation methods and tools.*
- *Notarnicola, B., et al. (2017). The role of life cycle assessment in supporting sustainable agri-food systems: A review of the challenges. Journal of Cleaner Production, 140, 399–409.*

Table of content

LCC (Life Cycle Costing)

Economic analysis

LCC means considering all the costs that will be incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service. Such as: a) purchase price and all associated costs, b) operating costs, including energy, fuel and water use, spares, and maintenance, c) end-of-life costs or residual value. LCC may also include the cost of externalities under specific conditions laid out in the directives.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Europe Union. (2022). *Life-cycle costing*.
- Gavalda, O., González, A., Raya, M., Owen, M., Kemausuor, F., & Arranz-Piera, P. (2022). *Life Cycle Cost analysis for industrial bioenergy projects: Development of a simulation tool and application to three demand sectors in Africa*. *Energy Reports*, 8, 2908–2923.

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LCSFM (Latent Class Stochastic Frontier Model)

Quantitative model

LCSFM is an error model, which is appropriate for use by researchers who do not have a clear idea of which firms fit with particular production technology or the number of various technologies in the sample (Mekonnen et al., 2015; Martinez Cillero et al., 2016).

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Mekonnen, D. K., et al. (2015). *Innovation systems and technical efficiency in developing-country agriculture*. *Agricultural Economics*, 46(5), 689-702.
- Dakpo, K. H., et al. (2021). *Latent class modelling for a robust assessment of productivity: Application to French grazing livestock farms*. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 72(3), 760-781.

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Linear programming models have been frequently employed to develop Agricultural production planning models. These models often integrate the production of various goods with various soil management and agricultural approaches, allowing for effective resource allocation and cost minimization.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Heady, E. O. (1954). *Simplified presentation and logical aspects of linear programming technique*. *Journal of Farm Economics*, 36(5), 1035-1048.
- McCorkle, C. O. (1955). *Linear programming as a tool in farm management analysis*. *Journal of Farm Economics*, 37(5), 1222-1235.
- Osaki, M., & Batalha, M. O. (2014). *Optimization model of agricultural production system in grain farms under risk, in Sorriso, Brazil*. *Agricultural Systems*, 127, 178-188.

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Linear Programming Module of NutriSurvey

Quantitative model

Linear programming is a mathematical tool which can give clear answers to very practical questions faced in the field by nutritionists working in developing countries. Linear programming is based on the examination of multiple inequalities at the same time.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Nutrisurvey. (2022). Linear Programming Module of NutriSurvey*
- *Briend, A., et al. (2003). Linear programming: A mathematical tool for analyzing and optimizing children's diets during the complementary feeding period. Journal of Pediatric Gastroenterology and Nutrition, 36(1), 12–22.*
- *Ferguson, E., et al.(2020). programming Recommendations using Linear Programming.*

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Logic Diagrams are used in a variety of inquiries and are frequently created iteratively. They can be used to show plausible causes, conditions, and occurrences to aid in selecting the cause scenario. They can also direct investigators to what more information or evidence should be collected to corroborate or deny a supposed cause scenario. They are very useful way to convey a control sequence in a generic format.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *ScienceDirect. (2022). Logic Diagram. ScienceDirect*

MAGNET (Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool)

Quantitative model

MAGNET is a standard, dynamic, global general equilibrium model, whose modular structure can be modified according to specific questions research is inquiring about. Researchers chose MAGNET to replicate the impacts of agricultural, trade, land, and bioenergy policies on the worldwide economy highlighting the impacts of land use, agricultural prices, nutrition, and household food security.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Woltjer, G. B., et al. (2014). *The MAGNET model: Module description (No. 14-57)*. LEI Wageningen UR.
- van Meijl, H., et al. (2018). *Comparing impacts of climate change and mitigation on global agriculture by 2050*. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(6), 064021

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Materiality Assessment

Exploratory and
participatory learning
methodology

Used to determine which impacts and dependencies are the most important and significant in relation to the issue of interest and what you will go on to measure and value. It provides a transparent way to communicate how and why you have limited the scope of the assessment by providing the rationale behind your choices. It informs the boundary decisions on the impact pathways and de-dependency pathways, ensuring a systemic view of the situation to be addressed.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Determine, explore, and question boundaries.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *IDDEA GROUP, & GLOBAL ALLIANCE FOR THE FUTURE OF FOOD. (2020). Applying the TEEBAgrifood Evaluation Framework. Overarching Implementation Guidance..*
- *Torelli, R., Balluchi, F., & Furlotti, K. (2020). The materiality assessment and stakeholder engagement: A content analysis of sustainability reports. Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management, 27(2), 470–484.*

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MCA expands the boundaries of the analysis beyond cost benefit or cost effectiveness results and allows the assessment of projects against a variety of criteria, including quantitative and qualitative indicators. MCAs can be conducted in cases where multiple objectives and decision criteria exist.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations.

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *TEEB. (2018). Chapter 7. Teebagrifood Methodology: An overview of evaluation and valuation methods and tools.*
- *Gésan-Guiziou, G., et al. (2020). Diversity and potentiality of multi-criteria decision analysis methods for agri-food research. Agronomy for Sustainable Development, 40(6).*
- *Aidonis, D., et al. (2015). Multi-criteria evaluation of sustainable supply chains in the agrifood sector. International Journal of Sustainable Agricultural Management and Informatics, 1(2), 106.*

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Measuring Distance to the SDG Targets

Secondary data review and analysis

This report aims to help OECD Member countries evaluate where they currently stand with regard to the SDGs, to assess the direction and pace of their recent trajectory, and to identify areas where additional effort is needed. It also sets out the statistical agenda ahead – showing how much we do not yet know and how this might affect both the achievement of the SDGs and decisions about what to prioritize across this vast agenda.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

-

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

 - Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations
-

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
-

Identification of potential transition pathways

 - Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

MATS findings

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- OCDE (2022). *The Short and Winding Road to 2030. Measuring Distance to the SDG Targets.* OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Cohen, G., & Shinwell, M. (2020). *How to measure distance to SDG targets anywhere.* 61.

MATS Case studies

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MetODD-SDG

Analytical framework
& indicators

MetODD-SDG is an assessment tool that lets mission-driven businesses measure their contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals. MetODD-SDG is a list of micro-level indicators for SDG Targets.

The assessment tool works iteratively with a list of indicators covering 73 Targets for 16 of the 17 SDGs by now.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- CERISE (2022). *MetODD-SDG*.
- Gurrieri, V., Landoni, P., & Moratti, A. (2024). *Environmental and Social Impact Assessment for Startups: A Project-Based Approach Towards Sustainability*. Politecnico di Torino.

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MIMES (Multi-scale Integrated Models of Ecosystem Services)

Mixed methods
model

MIMES uses a systems approach (in that it considers entire ecological systems, but not social and economic dynamics) to model changes in ecosystem services across a spatially explicit environment. The model quantifies the effects of land and sea use change on ecosystem services and can be run at global, regional, and local levels.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- AFORDable Futures LLC. (2022). *Dynamic Spatial Modeling - MIMES.*
- Othoniel, B., Rugani, B., Heijungs, R., Withagen, C., & Benetto, E. (2015). *The use of ecosystem services integrated modelling in LCA. World Conference on Natural Resource Modeling. 29th June - 1st July.*

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MIRAGE (Modelling International Relationships in Applied General Equilibrium)

Quantitative model

MIRAGE model is a multi-region, multi-sector computable general equilibrium model used to analyze trade policy (Bchir et al., 2002); it is a recursive dynamic model to deal with world structural change from medium to the very long-run horizon. It describes imperfect competition and horizontal product differentiation in a rather standard way, but with a new procedure, allowing the available information to be used more efficiently.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Bchir, M. H., Decreux, Y., Guérin, J. L., & Jean, S. (2003). *MIRAGE, a computable general equilibrium model for trade policy analysis*. CEPII Working Paper.
- Bellora, C., & Foure, J. (2018). *Value-added in a Computable General Equilibrium model with oligopolistic competition: drivers and implications of sourcing by agent in the MIRAGE-e model*.

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MODAM (Multi-Objective Decision Support Model for Agri-Ecosystem Management Model)

Quantitative model

MODAM, a static, process-based model with multi-objective linear programming. Its' goal is to assess the economic and environmental sustainability of crop and livestock production at the farm level.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Zander, P. M. (2003). *Agricultural land use and conservation options: a modelling approach*. PhD. Thesis, Wageningen University and Research, The Netherlands.
- Prato, T., Fulcher, C., Wu, S., & Ma, J. (1996). *Multiple-Objective Decision Making for Agroecosystem Management*. *Agricultural and Resource Economics Review*, 25(2), 200–212.

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77

MONICA (Model for Nitrogen and Carbon Dynamics in Agro-Ecosystems)

Quantitative model

MONICA, a dynamic, process-based model with a goal of simulation of crop growth and analysis of its relationship with soil characteristics in changing climate conditions and cropping practices.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Nendel, C., Berg, M., Kersebaum, K. C., Mirschel, W., Specka, X., Wegehenkel, M., ... & Wieland, R. (2011). The MONICA model: Testing predictability for crop growth, soil moisture and nitrogen dynamics. *Ecological Modelling*, 222(9), 1614-1625.
- Chu, M., Guzman, J., & Villamil, M. (2018). A Modeling Framework to Evaluate the Impacts of Future Climate on Soil Organic Carbon Dynamics. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 47(4), 596-606.

[Table of content](#)

National Computable General Equilibrium model

Quantitative model

It is an amplified national CGE model that combines economic factors with biophysical models which take into account land heterogeneity and market mechanisms. It is a static model, and it eliminates the impact of economical dynamic factors which may be unconnected with the bioethanol extension, the only variable factor that alters at the base year level of the model.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Weng, Y., Chang, S., Cai, W., & Wang, C. (2019). Exploring the impacts of biofuel expansion on land use change and food security based on a land explicit CGE model: A case study of China. *Applied Energy*, 236, 514-525

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Netmapping

Exploratory and participatory learning methodology

Net-Map is an interview-based mapping tool that helps people understand, visualize, discuss, and improve situations in which many different actors influence outcomes. By creating Influence Network Maps, individuals and groups can clarify their own view of a situation, foster discussion, and develop a strategic approach to their networking activities.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

-

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

 - Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations
-

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

 - Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
-

Identification of potential transition pathways

 - Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
 - Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.

MATS findings

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- IFPRI. (2007). *International Food Policy Research Institute. Tool Net-Map.*
- Yaméogo, T. B., Fonta, W. M., & Wünscher, T. (2018). *Can social capital influence smallholder farmers' climate-change adaptation decisions? Evidence from three semi-arid communities in Burkina Faso, West Africa. Social Sciences, 7(3), 1–20.*

MATS Case studies

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Guiding principles/
frameworks

Identification of sources of power concentrated at eight strategic nodes. In each nodes, is examined where the power is accumulated, the critical issues that surround that node, how the power may be leveraged, and potential methodological strategies for documenting it.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring power structures and dynamics.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Hendrickson, M., Wilkinson, J., Heffernan, W. D., & Gronski, R. (2011). The Global Food System and Nodes of Power. SSRN Electronic Journal.*

[Table of content](#)

Nutrition-sensitive Value Chain Analysis

Mapping instruments

Identify the constraints in supply and demand of commodities as they relate to the nutrition problem. This analysis differs from a standard VC analysis in that it specifically analyses dimensions that are relevant to nutrition, such as food safety, food loss, nutrition value or barriers to consumption from smallholders.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- De La Peña, I., & Garrett, J. (2018). *Nutrition-sensitive value chains. A guide for project design, Volume I.*
- Allen, S., & de Brauw, A. (2018). *Nutrition sensitive value chains: Theory, progress, and open questions. Global Food Security, 16*(July 2017), 22–28.
- De la Pena, I., Garrett, J., & Gelli, A. (2018). *Nutrition-sensitive value chains from a smallholder perspective: A framework for project design . In Go.Gale.Com (Issue January).*

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NWF (National Water-Food) modelling framework

Quantitative model

(NWF) modelling framework examines the broad links between the water use in different sectors, the population dynamics, and their compounding effects on a country's food gap and water self-sufficiency.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Alexandratos, N., & Bruinsma, J. (2012). *World agriculture towards 2030/2050: the 2012 revision*.
- Abdelkader, A., Elshorbagy, A., Tuninetti, M., Laio, F., Ridolfi, L. F. G. G. M., Fahmy, H., & Hoekstra, A. Y. (2018). *National water, food, and trade modeling framework: The case of Egypt*. *Science of the Total Environment*, 639, 485-496.

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Quantitative model

Standard OECD ENV-Linkages model is a global, general equilibrium, recursive dynamic model. The model can explore and quantify policy responses to a series of government environmental initiatives, through future projections of the link between economic activities and emissions.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Burniaux, J. M., & Chateau, J. (2008). *An overview of the OECD Env-linkages model*. OECD Economics Department Working Papers, No. 653, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Chateau, J., Rebelledo, C., & Dellink, R. (2011). *An Economic Projection to 2050: The OECD" ENV-Linkages" Model Baseline*.

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OECD-FAO Guidance for Responsible Agricultural Supply Chains

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Framework with SDGs indicators developed by a working group during the OECD-FAO Agricultural pilot project that illustrates how a company can use its due diligence process to contribute to the SDGs. It can support assessments of companies engaged across the whole value chain.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *OECD/FAO (2021), OECD-FAO Guidance for Responsible Agricultural Supply Chains - Helping achieve the SDGs, OECD Publishing, Paris.*

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Oxfam inequality guide

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Guide to tackling inequalities. It explains why certain issues could be relevant to your work, it provides questions to explore with your team and partners, and it gives options for actions for: (i) tackling power and political inequalities; (ii) strengthening transparency, accountability, citizen participation and space for civil society; (iii) raising public resources: aid, debt, and fair taxation; (iv) raising public resources: revenues from extractive industries; (v) spending public resources on progressive public services; (vi) jobs and wages; (vii) access to productive resources: land and capital; (viii) tackling gender inequalities.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring power structures and dynamics.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Oxfam. (2017). Oxfam Inequality Guide.*

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Problem tree

Exploratory and
participatory learning
methodology

Problem tree analysis (also called Situational analysis or just Problem analysis) helps to find solutions by mapping out the anatomy of cause and effect around an issue.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *MSP Guide. (2022b). Problem Tree. Tool 14.*
- *Ammani, A., Auta, S., & Aliyu, J. (2011). Challenges to Sustainability: Applying the Problem Tree Analysis Methodology to the ADP System in Nigeria. Journal of Agricultural Extension, 14(2), 35–45.*

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Qualitative scenarios

Future-oriented
planning tools

Long recognized as a cornerstone of foresight processes, scenarios, and the processes through which they are developed, are rich with opportunities to build anticipatory capacities and make an organization more prepared and resilient in the face of uncertainty and crises. Thus, developing scenarios through systems-level research coupled with rigorous imagination enables teams to develop 'futures literacy' and to inform and improve decisions and robust strategies in the present.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
- Designing transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Fraunhofer. (2022). *Communication and Participation for the Societal Transformation towards the Bioeconomy (BioKompass)*.
- Fraunhofer ISI. (2022a). *Digital Agricultural Knowledge and Information System (DAKIS). Innovative integration for landscape smart agriculture.*

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Quick Guide to Gender-Sensitive Indicators

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Guidance to developing gender-sensitive indicators.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Parvez Butt, A., Jayasinghe, N., & Zaaroura, M. (2019). *Integrating Gender in Research Planning*.
- OXFAM. (2014). *Quick Guide to Gender-Sensitive Indicators*. In Oxfam Gb.
- Quisumbing, Agnes,, et al. 2021. "Women's Empowerment and Gender Equality in Agricultural Value Chains: Evidence from Four Countries in Asia and Africa." *Food Security* 13 (5): 1101–24.

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Regression Models

Quantitative model

The models are used to perform impact evaluation, causal analysis, and forecasting. The primary goal of regression analysis is to estimate the causal effects of a policy on an outcome of interest to enhance the credibility of the estimated results.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

MATS findings

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Koondhar, M. A., et al. (2021). Green growth of cereal food production under the constraints of agricultural carbon emissions: A new insight from ARDL and VECM models. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 47, 101452.
- Iorga, E., Oancea C., & Stanca R. (2009). The analysis of variance transmission of the industrial production price on the consumer price variation. *Occasional Papers no. 26, National Bank of Romania.*

MATS Case studies

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Research guidelines for understanding estimates of economic inequality

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Guidelines document that introduces the fundamentals of how economic inequality is estimated, thus shedding light on the diversity of measures and data used for capturing inequality.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Mager, F. (2019). *Understanding Estimates of Economic Inequality*. 7.

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Rich Picture

Exploratory and
participatory learning
methodology

Rich picture is a drawing of a situation that illustrates the main elements and relationships that need to be considered in trying to intervene in order to create some improvement. It consists of pictures, text, symbols and icons, which are all used to illustrate graphically the situation. It is called a rich picture because it illustrates the richness and complexity of a situation.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *MSP Guide. (2022b). Rich Picture .*
- *Monk, A., & Howard, S. (1998). Methods & tools: the rich picture: a tool for reasoning about work context. Interactions, 5(2), 21–30.*
- *Grant, M., Gilgen, A. K., & Buchmann, N. (2019). The rich picture method: A simple tool for reflective teaching and learning about sustainable food systems. Sustainability (Switzerland), 11(18).*

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RISE (Response Inducing Sustainability Evaluation)

Analytical framework
& indicators

RISE is an a holistic, indicator-based sustainability tool focused on supporting farmers in distinguishing precise on-farm deficiencies in sustainability performance (e.g. environmental issues such as biodiversity, water usage, and soil quality; social and economic issues such as working conditions and economic viability) (Grenz et al., 2016).

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Grenz, J., Mainiero, R., Schoch, M., Sereke, F., Stalder, S., Thalmann, C., & Wyss, R. (2016). *RISE (Responce-InducingSustainability Evaluation), version 3.0.* Bern University of Applied Sciences School of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences: Zollikofen, Switzerland.
- Pineau -Ilw, M. (2008). *Bachelor Thesis-2008 RISE model for Livestock Water Productivity Improvement.*

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Roadmapping

Future-oriented
planning tools

It is a versatile tool to support strategic planning. Roadmaps depict future developments, events or measures over time. Common to all roadmaps is a reference to the future, the temporal linkage of the depicted aspects and the orientation towards a vision or a goal. Road mapping creates an orientation framework by identifying knowledge gaps and inconsistencies at an early stage and identifying appropriate measures in good time.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
- Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Specialisation, S., & Ris, S. (2021). INNOVATION UND FOR- SCHUNG SÜDTIROL 2030.*
- *Fraunhofer. (2022). Regionale Entwicklungsstrategie TechnologieRegion Karlsruhe 2030.*
- *Berner, S., Derler, H., Rehorska, R., Pabst, S., & Seebacher, U. (2019). Roadmapping to enhance local food supply: Case study of a city-region in Austria. Sustainability (Switzerland), 11(14), 1–16.*

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SAFA (Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agricultural Systems)

Secondary data
review and analysis

SAFA focuses on observation and self-assessment of enterprises in the food and agricultural sector with a goal of worldwide recognized standard for agriculture sustainability assessment.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *FAO (2013). SAFA Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems Indicators. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO): Rome, Italy*
- *Soldi, A., Meza, M. J. A., Guareschi, M., Donati, M., & Ortiz, A. I. (2019). Sustainability assessment of agricultural systems in Paraguay: A comparative study using FAO's SAFA framework. Sustainability (Switzerland), 11(13).*

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SALCA sustain methodology

Secondary data
review and analysis

SALCA sustain is an indicator-based sustainability method that evaluates dimensions and subjects. It is a more complex model compared to others that can give researchers answers to their queries and analyses of various farm management strategies.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Roesch, A., Nyfeler-Brunner, A., & Gaillard, G. (2021). Sustainability assessment of farms using SALCA sustain methodology. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 27, 1392-1405

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SAM (Social Accounting Matrix) - based multiplier analysis

Economic analysis

SAM is a representation of the macro and meso economic accounts of a socio-economic system, which capture the transitions and transfers between all economic agents in the system. SAM helps to bring together data from disparate sources to describe the structural characteristics of an economy. It is also a good way of illustrating income distribution and economic structure. Lastly, it is a useful framework for modelling.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Deb Pal, B., Pohit, S., & Roy, J. (2012). *SOCIAL ACCOUNTING MATRIX FOR INDIA*. *Economic Systems Research*, 24(1), 77–99.
- Round, J. (n.d.). *Social Accounting Matrices and SAM-based Multiplier Analysis*. In *ToolKit*.

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Scenario Planning

Future-oriented
planning tools

Scenario Planning uses stories of what could happen in the future with diverse stakeholders in order to decide jointly how they want to influence the future. Scenarios consist of a range of multiple stories or hypotheses to capture a range of future possibilities, both good and bad. They include diverse external issues, which might evolve. Scenario planning consists of the process through which scenarios are developed and how they are used to inform strategic planning.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- Designing transition pathways.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *MSP Guide. (2022c). Scenario Planning. Tool 36.*
- *Chermack, T. J., & Lynham, S. A. (2002). Definitions and Outcome Variables of Scenario Planning. Human Resource Development Review, 1(3), 366–383.*

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SDG Trade Monitor

Secondary data
review and analysis

It is a free analytical portal to track down the progress made in the area of international trade toward the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals. SDG Trade Monitor allows to conduct customized analysis using official trade-related SDG indicators and other complementary indicators to provide you with a more extensive understanding of the relation between trade and development in the SDG agenda.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- ITC, UNCTAD, & WTO. (2022). *Analyse the contribution of international trade to economic development with the SDG Trade Monitor.*
- Siegel, K. M., & Bastos Lima, M. G. (2020). *When international sustainability frameworks encounter domestic politics: The sustainable development goals and agri-food governance in South America.* *World Development*, 135, 105053.

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SEEA AFF (System of Environmental-Economic Accounting for Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries)

Guiding principles/
frameworks

SEEA AFF is a subsystem of the SEEA Central Framework that organizes data to analyze the relationship between the environment and economic activities in these sectors. It extends SEEA CF methods, providing tables for measuring assets and flows related to production, trade, and consumption. SEEA AFF supports reporting of agri-environmental indicators for international processes like the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the Climate Convention.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *FAO, & División de Estadística de las Naciones Unidas. (2020). System of Environmental-Economic Accounting for Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries.*
- *King, S., et al. (2024). Using the system of environmental-economic accounting ecosystem accounting for policy: A case study on forest ecosystems. Environmental Science & Policy, 152, 103653.*

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SNA (Social Network Analysis)

Mixed methods
model

SNA is a set of techniques for analyzing social systems. It can be used to understand networks and their participants, that is, to grasp and describe the organization of the networks as a whole as well as the position of individual actors. It offers a variety of techniques for measuring, visualizing, and simulating relationships and allows analyzing these relationships in visual as well as mathematical terms. SNA essentially provides a set of representational techniques for the analysis of social ties. It assumes that social ties matter because they influence behaviour or transmit information and goods.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Williams, B., & Hummelbrunner, R. (2009). *Systems concepts in action: a practitioner's toolkit*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press. pp. 60-74
- Clark, L. (2010). *Seeing the social capital in agricultural innovation systems: using SNA to visualise bonding and bridging ties in rural communities*. *Knowledge Management for Development Journal*, 6(3), 206–218.

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Exploratory and
participatory learning
methodology

Explore a situation from different perspectives, mobilizing stakeholders to negotiate their goals, expectations, and interests. Oriented towards learning and insights.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes..
- Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Williams, B., & Hummelbrunner, R. (2009). *Systems concepts in action: a practitioner's toolkit*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press. pp. 241-261
- Tavella, E., & Hjortsø, C. N. (2012). *Enhancing the design and management of a local organic food supply chain with soft Systems Methodology*. *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review*, 15(2), 47–68.

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STATA

Statistics tool

STATA is general-purpose statistical software. Stata possesses both a command-line interface and a point-and-click menu interface, with a one-to-one correspondence between the two. Stata appeals to researchers from a wide range of fields, with concentrations in the health sciences and in economics.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

 MATS findings

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

GREATLY
CONTRIBUTE

Stakeholders engagement:

AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Gutierrez, R. G. (2010). *Stata*. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Statistics*, 2(6), 728–733.
- Oliveira, M. de F., & Reis, P. (2023). *Portuguese Agrifood Sector Resilience: An Analysis Using Structural Breaks Applied to International Trade*. *Agriculture 2023*, Vol. 13, Page 1699, 13(9), 1699.

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Surveys

Stakeholders' consultation tools

Survey is a method of data collection using questionnaires or interviews administered to a representative sample of a population, used to gather information on opinions, behaviors, and demographic characteristics, facilitating the analysis of trends and patterns.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

-

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

 - Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations
-

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
 - Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.
 - Exploring power structures and dynamics
-

Identification of potential transition pathways

 - Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
 - Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
 - Providing political/ actionable recommendations
 - Determine, explore, and question boundaries.
 - Designing transition pathways.

MATS findings

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Passmore, C., et al. (2022). *Guidelines for Constructing a Survey*. Research Series, 34.
- Song, H., & Chen, K. (2010). *Trade Effects and Compliance Costs of Food Safety Regulations: the Case of China*. *Agriculture and Agricultural Science Procedia*, 1, 429–438.
- Giovannetti, G., & Marvasi, E. (2016). *Food exporters in global value chains: Evidence from Italy*. *Food Policy*, 59, 110–125.

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SUSFANS

Secondary data
review and analysis

This Visualizer gives insight into the sustainability performance of European diets and food systems for the years 2010 to 2050. It is based on the metrics, models and foresight developed in the SUSFANS project.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *SUSFANS. (2015). Metrics, Models and Foresight for European SUSTainable Food And Nutrition Security. Exploring The European Food System.*
- *Rutten, M., et al. (2018). Metrics, models and foresight for European sustainable food and nutrition security: The vision of the SUSFANS project. Agricultural Systems, 163(2018), 45–57.*

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SWAT (The Soil and Water Assessment Tool)

Spatial models

SWAT is a small watershed to river basin-scale model used to simulate the quality and quantity of surface and ground water and predict the environmental impact of land use, land management practices, and climate change. SWAT is widely used in assessing soil erosion prevention and control, non-point source pollution control and regional management in watersheds.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- SWAT. (2022). *Soil & Water Assessment Tool*.
- Douglas-Mankin, K. R., Srinivasan, R., & Arnold, J. G. (2010). *Soil and water assessment tool (SWAT) model: Current developments and applications*. *Transactions of the ASABE*, 53(5), 1423–1431.
- Bressiani, D. de A, et al. (2015). *A review of soil and water assessment tool (SWAT) applications in Brazil: Challenges and prospects*. *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, 8(3), 1–27.

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Systems dynamics modelling approach

Quantitative model

Facilitate better understanding of the dynamic behaviour of complex systems, by clarifying the underlying mental models and generating scenarios of systems behaviour over time. It has been widely used in research related to agricultural land, soil, and water resources management, as well as in the examination of the resilience in food systems to address complex and non-linear feedback systems.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Stermann, J. (2000). *Business Dynamics*, 1st ed.; McGraw-Hill, Inc.: New York, NY, USA.
- Williams, B., & Hummelbrunner, R. (2009). *Systems concepts in action: a practitioner's toolkit*. Stanford, California: Stanford University Press. pp. 45-59
- Abdelkader, A., et al. (2018). National water, food, and trade modeling framework: The case of Egypt. *Science of the Total Environment*, 639, 485-496

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TCD (Trade Competitiveness Diagnostic Toolkit)

Toolkit

TCD toolkit provides a framework, guidelines, and practical tools needed to conduct an analysis of trade competitiveness. The toolkit can be used to assess the competitiveness of a country's overall basket of exports, as well as specific traded sectors. It includes guidance on a range of tools and indicators that can be used to analyze trade performance in terms of growth, orientation, diversification, quality, and survival, as well as quantitative and qualitative approaches to analyze the market and supply-side factors that determine competitiveness.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

 MATS findings

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

SLIGHTLY
CONTRIBUTE

Stakeholders engagement:

NOT INVOLVED

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Reis, J. G., & Farole, T. (2012). Trade Competitiveness Diagnostic Toolkit. In Trade Competitiveness Diagnostic Toolkit.

MATS Case studies

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The Gravity Approach

Quantitative model

The Gravity Approach explains international or regional trade. The model uses a function to relate the trade flows between countries to the distance between the origin and destination countries and the various explanatory variables related to the characteristics of both origin and destination countries.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Sen, A., and Smith, T. E. (1995) *Gravity models of spatial interaction behavior*, Berlin: Springer-Verlag.
- Anderson, J. E. (1979). *A theoretical foundation for the gravity equation*. *The American Economic Review*, 69(1), 106-116.
- Anderson, J. E., & Van Wincoop, E. (2004). *Trade costs*. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 42(3), 691-751.

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Three-step methodology to assess food systems vulnerability

Exploratory and participatory learning methodology

It adapts a vulnerability framework (Fraser et al., 2011) in combination with participatory scenario analysis. It allows including the agency of agri-food system actors and normative issues in the research. 1. Vulnerability of what and to what? – Selection of drivers of change. 2. Vulnerability for whom? At which scale? – Exploring different narratives of historical and current perceptions of change, exposure, and impacts of local agri-food system. 3. Envisioning future trajectories of transformation through participatory scenario analysis.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes..
- Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Vallejo-Rojas, V., et al. (2016). *Developing an integrated framework to assess agri-food systems and its application in the Ecuadorian Andes. Regional Environmental Change*, 16(8), 2171–2185.
- Molderink, A., et al. (2010). *A three-step methodology to improve domestic energy efficiency. Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference, ISGT 2010*, 1–8.

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TOA (Tradeoff Analysis)

Future-oriented
planning tools

TOA is an approach to positive analysis that combines foresight analysis and simulation modelling tools from the relevant disciplines, including economics, in a participatory process designed to formulate and evaluate forward-looking, strategic decisions under high levels of uncertainty in complex systems.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.
- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
- Designing transition pathways.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Antle, J. M., & Valdivia, R. O. (2021). Trade-off analysis of agri-food systems for sustainable research and development. *Q Open*, 1(1), 1–34.
- Antle, J. M., & Valdivia, R. O. (2021). Trade-off analysis of agri-food systems for sustainable research and development. *Q Open*, 1(1)

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TRIMAG (Tariff Reduction Impact Model for Agriculture)

Quantitative model

TRIMAG model evaluates the impacts of domestic prices from the standard and sensitive tariff cut, based on an 8-digit level database on domestic (Swiss) tariffs, prices and import flows from the EU and the Rest of the World, with the prices and consumption as calculated in the context of WTO negotiations. TRIMAG is capable to estimate for 90 agricultural commodities a list of all the potential impacts on domestic prices from tariff reductions. Furthermore, it can be used as a tool for other partial or general equilibrium models.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Exploring different scenarios to gain insights on the system's behavior and outcomes.

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Listorti, G., Kempen, M., Girardin, J., & Kranzlein, T. (2011). Do price uncertainties affect the use of policy flexibilities? The selection of sensitive products in WTO agricultural negotiations (No. 726-2016-49878).
- Listorti, G., Tonini, A., Kempen, M., & Adenauer, M. (2013). How to implement WTO scenarios in simulation models: linking the TRIMAG tariff aggregation tool to CAPRI (No. 710-2016-48483).

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Typical Farm

Guiding principles/
frameworks

Typical farm is a model farm representing the most common farm type for a specific product in a specific country or region. The necessary technical and economic data to define the typical farm were established by farmers and local experts. Since a worldwide farm accountancy system does not exist, the typical farm approach is a good tool to compare the total cost of production per unit and other indicators of farm performances across different countries.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

MATS findings

HIGHLY
CONTRIBUTE

HIGHLY
CONTRIBUTE

HIGHLY
CONTRIBUTE

AS A SOURCE OF INFORMATION

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- European Commission. (2014). *Assessing farmers' cost of compliance with EU legislation in the fields of environment, animal welfare and food safety*. 277.
- Menghi, A., et al. (2014). *Assessing farmers' cost of compliance with EU legislation in the fields of environment, animal welfare and food safety. FINAL REPORT*. European Commission Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development.

MATS Case studies

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UKAMM (UK Agricultural Market Model)

Quantitative model

UKAMM is a system of consumption patterns, production processes, and international trade flows, mainly used to describe economic relationships regarding the sectors of dairy, crops, oilseed processing, livestock, and sugar.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs UK (2021). *Modelling agriculture in the UK*.
- Jacobs, A., & Youngman, T. (2022, April). *Can diet change meet climate targets?*

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Value Chain Analysis

Mapping instruments

Study of the “full range of activities which are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the different phases of production (involving a combination of physical transformation and the input of various producer services), delivery to final consumers, and final disposal after use” (Kaplinsky and Morris, 2001, pg. 4).

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

-

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

 - Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations
-

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

 - Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
-

Identification of potential transition pathways

MATS findings

Stakeholders engagement:

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Kaplinsky, R., & Morris, M. (2001). *A Handbook for Value Chain Research*. ResearchGate.
- Taylor, D. H. (2005). *Value chain analysis: An approach to supply chain improvement in agri-food chains*. *International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management*, 35(10), 744–761.

MATS Case studies

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Visioning processes deal with desirable futures. A vision clearly and inspiringly describes a desirable future for all group members. In terms of methodology, the most important thing in visioning processes is to create a space in which an open exchange about values and one's own situation is possible and encouraged.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

- Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system
- Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes
- Identification of potential transition pathways
 - Determine, explore, and question boundaries.
 - Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *Cimulatac. (2017). CIMULACT -Building visions for Europe.*
- *Warnke, P., & Röß, A. (2017). A clear and inspiring description of a group's preferred future. Fraunhofer.*
- *Halbe, J. & Adamowski, J. (2019). Modeling Sustainability visions: A Case study of multi-scale food systems in Southwestern Ontario. Journal of Environmental Management. 231. pp. 1028-1047*

Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSS) Assessment Toolkit

Toolkit

VSS Assessment Toolkit guide the identification of the challenges and perceptions behind the adoption of a VSS scheme, from mapping the value chain of interest and its stakeholders to exploring policy options to address them. The assessment consists of five steps: 1) Value Chain Mapping, 2) Interviews, 3) Survey, 4) Analysis, and 5) Policy Options.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

- Exploring power structures and dynamics.
- Mapping and analyzing elements and linkages to explore the dynamics of complex systems.
- Mapping social structures and networks within complex systems.

Identification of potential transition pathways

- Providing political/ actionable recommendations.
- Exploring different perspectives and fostering exchanges and collective learning.

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- *United Nations. (2022). The UNCTAD Approach to Voluntary Sustainability Standards.*
- *UNCTAD. (2020a). Assessment of organic certification in the coconut oil value chain in the Philippines. Fostering the development of green exports through voluntary sustainability standards.*

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WGI (Worldwide Governance Indicators)

Analytical framework
& indicators

WGI project reports aggregate individual governance indicators for over 200 countries and territories over the period 1996–2020, for six dimensions. These aggregate indicators combine the views of a large number of enterprise, citizen and expert survey respondents in industrial and developing countries. They are based on over 30 individual data sources produced by a variety of survey institutes, think tanks, non-governmental organizations, international organizations, and private sector firms.

Contributions to Agricultural Trade analysis:

Data collection & analysis to make sense of the system

- Gathering and analyzing information to make sense of complex situations

Exploration of elements and linkages that determine the system's behavior and outcomes

Identification of potential transition pathways

Wanting to know more about the instrument?

Key literature

- Worldbank. (2021). *Worldwide Governance Indicators. Interactive Data Access*
- Kaufmann, D., Kraay, A., & Mastruzzi, M. (2010a). Response to “what do the worldwide governance indicators measure?” *European Journal of Development Research*, 22(1), 55–58.

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³ This references list responds to the references used in developing the text of this deliverable. Each of the tools is accompanied by specific references and cases of application.

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